

ECONOMIC TERMS OF TOURISM IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY.

Davlatova Shaxnoza Muhammadiyevna

Mardanova Mohira Davron qizi

Denov Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy.

Teacher of the Department of Foreign Language and Literature

Annotation: Tourism, with its multifaceted structure, affects all spheres of society's life is actively influencing. It will develop many aspects of the economy makes it possible. Tourism is a complex and complex sector of the world economy which has a significant impact on the entire world economy. Separately it applies equally to the economy of countries and regions. Some International tourism is the only source of foreign exchange earnings in these countries.

Keywords: tourism, export, import, economy, modernization, service, country development.

TURIZMNI MAMLAKAT IQTISODIYOTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI IQTISODIY ATAMALAR O'RNI

Davlatova Shaxnoza Muhammadiyevna

Denov tadbirkorlik va pedagogika instituti.

Xorijiy tili va adabiyoti kafedrası o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Turizm o'zining ko'p qirrali tuzilishi bilan jamiyat hayotining barcha sohalariga faol ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Bu iqtisodiyotning ko'plab jabhalarini rivojlantirishga imkon beradi. Turizm jahon iqtisodiyotining murakkab va murakkab tarmog'i bo'lib, butun jahon iqtisodiyotiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Alohida-alohida, u mamlakatlar va mintaqalar iqtisodiyotiga teng darajada qo'llaniladi. Ayrim Xalqaro turizm bu mamlakatlarda valyuta tushumlarining yagona manbai hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm, eksport, import, iqtisodiyot, modernizatsiya, xizmat ko'rsatish, mamlakat taraqqiyoti.

Today, tourism is one of the fastest growing and leading industries in terms of income. In recent years, tourism has become a major contributor to world exports, accounting for 11% of global GDP. Over the past 40 years, the number of tourists visiting other countries has increased 20 times, the income from tourism has increased 60 times, and the income from international tourism has reached 400 billion dollars. In

particular, deepening the liberalization of the economy, modernization of the country, and sustainable development of all sectors, especially tourism, which is one of the leading sectors of the service sector, are the basis of the success achieved in Uzbekistan. As the President of the Republic IAKarimov noted, "It is clear to all of us that the service sector is the most important source and factor of sustainable development of our economy. World experience today shows that this sector takes a leading role in forming the gross domestic product, ensuring employment of the population, and improving people's well-being". In fact, the rapid development of the tourism sector, which is an important component of the service network, is one of the priority areas of our country's economy. Tourism is the main driver of world civilization, and nowadays travel is the basis of human goals. In particular, prospects for the development of national tourism will help to increase the position of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan in the world market. As a proof of our opinion, we believe that it is permissible to point out that today great progress is being made in the field of tourism, it is increasing rapidly, new hotels are being built, the number of working places is increasing, the number of qualified specialists is increasing, and the flow of tourists is increasing year by year. Of course, taking into account the favorable climatic conditions and unique landscape of Uzbekistan, there are all grounds for the development of sports and ecological tourism. Farg'ana valley and Tashkent region are rich in magnificent mountain systems, blooming valleys and wonderful mountain rivers. The clean air of the mountain, the abundance of sunny days throughout the year, and the wonderful mountain scenery are the tourism facilities visited not only by the citizens of Uzbekistan, but also by the residents of neighboring countries such as Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan. Various types of mineral waters are widespread in Uzbekistan, many people visit more than 300 healing underground mineral water sources in the country. Currently, 121 of these sources are operating. There are several mountain resorts, such as Chimyon and Tortkol, where it is possible to develop mountain skiing. High snow mountains allow to realize different types of mountain tourism, such as mountaineering, speleotourism, river tourism. The abundance of medicinal herbs provides an opportunity to organize different ecological types, different herbs and species for collecting plants. This arouses interest among many foreign tourists. Assessing the current state of tourism, it is important to note that the level of infrastructure development in Uzbekistan does not fully meet the needs of foreign tourists. The underdevelopment of the infrastructure is caused by the previous administrative-command system, which did not allow to encourage competition and improvement. If the infrastructure is not sufficiently developed, it is impossible to increase the flow of tourists and, accordingly, to increase foreign exchange earnings.

Based on this, the state of the infrastructure has a direct impact on the development of tourism and the formation of the country's image.

First of all, it should be noted that until the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, not enough attention was paid to tourism. There was no objective information and advertising about the tourism potential of the republic. It can be said that the infrastructure of tourism, service and entertainment is not developed, the level of service to tourists is low, and there are no contacts with the world's leading tourist enterprises. Currently, tourism infrastructure is not evenly distributed in the territory of Uzbekistan. 36% of the republic's tourism potential is concentrated in Tashkent city and region. A region with a large infrastructure potential (Tashkent, Samarkand, Uzbekistan, among economists M.Pardaev, R.Atabaev, ISTukhliev, FXKudratov, N.Tuhliev, T.Abdullaeva, A.S.Soliev, M.R.Usmanov, MMMuhammedov, D.K.Usmanova, M.Koshimov, A.Norchavuraev,

B. .Norchaev, A.A.Eshtaev conducted scientific research in the field of tourism [2]. Tourism as a component of the economy brings income to the country receiving tourists, provides high foreign exchange earnings, increases the level of employment of the population. A hotel is needed to serve tourists. Here they have to eat. They enter and participate in various performances. In many cases, if they are foreign tourists, they provide an increase in foreign exchange earnings. Tourism is not only an economic but also an important social sector. Along with its economic efficiency, it is spiritual, spiritual and intellectual. because of this, the state pays special attention to this sector and provides certain benefits b treats People use these benefits just because they are tourists. This also indicates the unique nature of tourism and its great socio-economic importance. Privileges are manifested when tourists pass through customs posts, pay taxes, allow their passports when leaving the country, get tickets for air and railway transport, and process them. Tourism also has great benefits for the local population. They will be provided with work, they will communicate with representatives of different nationalities, peoples and peoples and get acquainted with their different traditions and values, they will have the opportunity to earn a permanent income, they will have the opportunity to sell products, the local population will be able to preserve their traditions as much as possible. and they continue to improve their hospitality traditions while restoring their traditional values. In the end, the outlook and cultural level of the local population will increase steadily. while restoring their motherland, they improve the traditions of hospitality. In the end, the outlook and cultural level of the local population will increase steadily. while restoring their motherland, they improve the traditions of hospitality. In the end, the outlook and cultural level of the local population will increase steadily. The development of tourism is also very useful

for the state. In particular, due to the development of tourism, he achieves the growth of the economy, ensures an increase in revenues to the state budget, achieves the preservation of natural resources, tries to ensure the social stability of the country and achieves it, achieves international relations, expands cultural relations, increases foreign exchange earnings, etc. Tourism can have both positive and negative effects on the lives of local residents.

Its positive features are as follows:

- creation of working conditions;
- increase of income, increase of standard of living of local population;
- acceleration of the urbanization process, development of urban services, infrastructure, cultural organizations;
- acceleration of social and cultural processes;
- creation of local cultural centers, development of folk art, traditions, customs;
- Increase in demand for agricultural products and locally produced goods;
- restoration and protection of local cultural monuments;
- natural complexes expansion;
- increasing the attractiveness of the region;
- revitalization of local cultural life;

The negative features are as follows:

- increase in the share of unskilled labor;
- increase in violations of public norms (drinking, prostitution, hooliganism);
- "erosion" of the family (family divorces, dissensions, etc.);
- between local residents and tourists, etc.

Analyzing the development of tourism in Uzbekistan, we can observe that the attention to the field of tourism in our country has increased and the number of visitors has increased.

Separation of essentials from the various groups of travel consists in the fact that the concrete type of tourism largely determines the sum of services by type and pricing. The nature of the tour operator's activity, the nature of the host region, marketing and many other parameters that take the place of the leading activity in the management of the tourist business. The most common indicators for the classification of international tourism are the type of offer, the method of organizing the trip, the purpose of the trip, and the method of movement. Leisure and recreational tourism includes various types of tourism for the purpose of recreation, sightseeing, sports, exotic vacations, thematic trips. In the classification by type of offers, group and individual foreign tourism is understood. In the tourism business, there are a number of terms that professionals understand each other half-heartedly. The terms FIT and GROUP are the most

commonly used terms. FIT foreign independent traveler is called individual tourist in Russian. He sets the itinerary and schedule of the trip as he pleases. A single tourist can use the service of a travel agency. But it is also possible to organize a trip independently. For example, through the Internet. Complex service is the main type of services offered for group tourism. A tourist buys a tour package. The sum of services added to the tour price is recorded in it. Usually the price of the tour package is lower than the sum of the value of some services included in the tour package. The group tour package is issued with a group voucher. Group tourists receive comprehensive services in return. This includes air transportation, hotel accommodation, catering, excursions and other services. Classification according to the organization of the trip. Organized tourism is a trip organized by a tourist company for individual or group tourists. Organized tourists have the right to purchase tour packages with various services from tour operators or their agents. Classification by purpose of travel. Depending on the main purpose, BTT divides the trip into the following groups:

- Rest and recreation;
- Social goals;
- Work-related and professional goals;
- Visiting friends and relatives;
- Religious (pilgrimage).

Tourist infrastructure includes hotels, catering establishments, a collection of communication routes, communications, organizations, shops, sports facilities and is closely connected with tourist service enterprises. It is aimed at ensuring the necessary conditions of the tourist infrastructure, the safety and health of tourists. In conclusion, it can be said that today tourism is recognized as one of the most profitable industries. In this regard, many countries are developing a number of programs for the development of tourism. The tourism sector also has great potential in increasing the economic potential of our country. Tourism will become one of the leading industries in our country as a result of the work carried out mainly on the development of international tourism.

Tourism is:

- a) travel (visit), a journey of an individual to any place outside of the usual place of residence for specific purposes, that is, activities that visitors perform outside the place of permanent residence from the moment of departure to return;
- b) business activities for the provision of services to the visitor related to the planning and organization of the trip and the implementation of the package of services providing the trip.

Types of tourism - internal, inbound and outbound:

domestic tourism - travel around the country by permanent residents;

inbound tourism - a trip around the country by permanent residents of other countries;

Outbound tourism is the travel of permanent residents of one country to another country.

International tourism includes inbound and outbound tourism;

National tourism consists of domestic and outbound tourism;

Domestic tourism is divided into inbound and domestic tourism.

A tourist is a citizen who visits a place of temporary residence (or place) for specific purposes, without engaging in remunerated activities in the host country, and stays in this country for at least one night.

According to international standards, the period of stay should not exceed 12 consecutive months, according to national standards - 6 months. A tourist as a consumer is a client of a tour operator or travel agent.

The main difference between a tourist and a tourist is that an excursionist is a citizen who visits to get to know the country (place) where the excursionist is temporarily. tourist resources for no more than 24 hours without providing accommodation services. An excursionist as a consumer is a client of the excursion desk.

Tourism industry - hotels and other means of accommodation, transport, entertainment and trade, public catering, educational, business and other facilities, organizations engaged in the activities of tour operators and travel agencies, as well as a set of organizations that provide excursion services and guide-interpreter services, travel (other services necessary for the organization and implementation of trips).

Tourist infrastructure - communication routes (roads, access roads, railway stations, airports, marinas, etc.), communications (water supply, electricity and gas networks, heat, sewage, means of communication, etc.), tourist resources , tourist exhibition facilities, accommodation and catering facilities, commercial facilities, household and treatment-preventive services, sports facilities, as well as other facilities necessary for the maintenance and development of the tourism industry .

Tourism resources - natural, historical, socio-cultural and other objects in the country (place) of temporary stay, including tourist exhibition objects, which can satisfy the spiritual needs of tourists and excursionists, restore and develop them other facilities that help. mental and physical strength. Tourism resources include specially protected natural areas (SPAs), as well as health resorts and spas.

References:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasining «Turizm to‘g‘risida»gi qonuni, O‘zbekistonning yangi qonunlari. Toshkent, Adolat, 2000.
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining «O‘zbekturizm Milliy Kompaniyasini tashkil qilish to‘g‘risida»gi farmoni. №PF-447. Xalq so‘zi, 1992, 22.
3. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 1995 yil 2 iyundagi 1162 raqamli «Buyuk Ipak Yo‘li»ni qayta tiklashda O‘zbekiston Respublikasining ishtirokini avj oldirish va respublikada xalqaro turizmni rivojlantirish borasidagi chora-tadbirlar to‘g‘risida»gi farmoni. Xalq so‘zi. 1995. 3-iyun.
4. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining «O‘zbekiston Respublikasida 2006-2010 yillarda xizmat ko‘rsatish va servis sohasini rivojlantirishni jadallashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida»gi 325- sonli qarori, 17- aprel 2006.
5. Aliyeva M.T., Umarjonov A.. «Turistik mamlakatlar iqtisodiyoti». Toshkent, Moliya, 2005.
6. Aliyeva M.T., Salimova B.X. «Mehmonxona menejmenti». Toshkent, 2007.
7. Aliyeva M.T. Xasanov L.G.«Organizatsiya turistik marshrutov» Toshkent, 2007.
8. Axmadxo‘jayev X., Mamarasulov X., Madiyorov F. «Marketing tadqiqotlari» Toshkent, 2002.
9. Aleksandrova L.Yu. Geografiya turizma. Moskva, 2008.
10. Axmedov X.I., Allaberganov A.A. Organizatsiya turistik deyatelnosti. Tashkent, 2004.
11. Birjakov M.B. «Vvedeniye v turizm». Izdatelstvo dom Gerda, 2006.
12. Durovich A.P. «Organizatsiya turizma» Moskva 2005.
13. Kvartalnov V.A. «Teoriya i praktika turizma». Moskva, «Finansi i statistika». Moskva, 2003.
14. Mamatqulov X.M. «Xalqaro turizm» Samarqand, 2008.
15. Nabiyeva S.A., I.A.Axmedov «Ekskursiyashunoslik» Toshkent, 2005.
16. Pardayev M.Q., Ataboyev R. Turizm asoslari. SamISI, Samarqand 2006.
17. Pardayev M.Q., Ataboyev R. Turistik resurslari tahlil qilish va baholash. SamISI, Samarqand 2006